

Advantages of a synchrotron light source for fluorescence-detected linear dichroism

Nykola C. Jones¹

¹ISA, Department of Physics and Astronomy, Aarhus University, Aarhus, Denmark

²School of Natural Sciences, Macquarie University, Sydney, New South Wales, Australia

³Research School of Chemistry, Australian National University, Canberra, ACT, Australia

⁴Department of Chemistry, University of Warwick, Coventry, UK

Correspondence

Alison Rodger, Research School of Chemistry, Australian National University, Canberra, ACT 2601, Australia.

Email: alison.rodger@anu.edu.au

Nykola C. Jones, ISA, Department of Physics and Astronomy, Aarhus University, Aarhus, Denmark.
nykj@phys.au.dk

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Abstract

Fluorescence-detected linear dichroism (FD-LD) enables one to collect linear dichroism spectra for oriented fluorophores in the presence of other absorbing species and light scattering. The experiment proceeds by scanning the excitation wavelength and using a filter to collect only emitted photons from the fluorophore. Thus, it has the potential to give data with enhanced selectivity and quality. By using a synchrotron radiation light source and fluorescence-detection, we show data for a range of fluorophores in different orienting environments. Film and flow-oriented FD-LD spectra were collected down to 170 nm. Even for flow-oriented liposomes, we have data collected down to 210 nm. For strongly scattering samples, for example, liposomes, FD-LD has the clear advantage that scattering is absent for the longer wavelength fluorescence photons. The collimated and smaller beam size of the synchrotron radiation also gives rise to sharper and more well-defined features in the spectra.

KEYWORDS

Couette flow, FD-LD, fluorescence detected linear dichroism, LD, stretched films, synchrotron radiation

1 | INTRODUCTION

The potential of fluorescence detected linear dichroism (FD-LD) to give clear linear dichroism (LD) spectra of

oriented fluorophores in the presence of background noise has previously been illustrated for stretched films,¹ flow-oriented molecules (e.g., DNA and protein fibers),² and analytes embedded in liposomal membranes.³ FD-

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LD thus enables orientation data to be measured for fluorophores which are in solution with nonfluorophores that absorb or scatter light, though one needs to assess whether absorbance or scattering could differentially attenuate the fluorescence polarizations.⁴

The attraction of LD spectroscopy is that it is the differential absorbance of light polarized parallel and perpendicular to an orientation direction and thus gives geometric information on the molecular level. For uniaxial orientation,

$$LD = (A_{\parallel} - A_{\perp}) = \frac{3}{2}AS(3\cos^2\alpha - 1) \quad (1)$$

where A is the sample absorbance, \parallel denotes parallel to an orientation axis, \perp denotes perpendicular to it, S is the orientation parameter (1 for perfect orientation, 0 for no orientation), and α is the angle between the orientation direction and the transition moment of interest. The reduced LD

$$LD' = \frac{3}{2}S(3\cos^2\alpha - 1) \quad (2)$$

is often used to present data as it is independent of concentration and extinction coefficient. The FD-LD when collected with the voltage on the photomultiplier tube (PMT) fixed at a constant value and a long-pass cut-off filter inserted after the sample is directly proportional to the LD¹⁻³

$$FD - LD(\text{fixed } HT, \text{ filter}) \approx -\phi I_0 J_2(\delta_0) LD \quad (3)$$

where ϕ is the quantum yield of the transition of interest, I_0 is the incident light intensity, J_2 is the second order Bessel function of the first kind, and δ_0 is the photoelastic modulators phase-shift amplitude. The latter is set to 0.765π such that the zeroth-order Bessel function $J_0 = 0$ as is custom for LD measurements (see, e.g., Hicks et al.⁵). Thus, the fixed HT FD-LD depends on the quantum yield (ϕ) and I_0 the incident intensity (which may be changed by changing instrument parameters) as well as the LD. For further details and also data collection in fixed-DC mode; see earlier studies.¹⁻³

This work was motivated by the fact that we are attracted to the ability of FD-LD to selectively probe any fluorophore(s) in an oriented sample,¹⁻³ but as with LD and circular dichroism (CD) on a bench-top instrument, our experiments suffered from loss of Xe-lamp light intensity below 200 nm. This work shows that synchrotron radiation (SR) does indeed deliver an extended wavelength range for measurement, as well as further advantages outlined below.

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Materials

All chemicals including gramicidin D, anthracene, and pyrene were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (North Ryde, NSW, Australia) or through VWR (Denmark). Liposomes were prepared by co-dissolving the analyte with L- α -phosphatidyl choline (typeIV-S) from soybean (40%) in a glass flask, drying the sample to a thin layer with air or nitrogen, and resuspending the mixture by addition of water (18.2 M Ω .cm) followed by five cycles of 30 s sonication yielding cloudy white solutions.⁶ We previously found using dynamic light scattering that this method produced an average particle size of 100 nm with quite a broad size distribution and that some analytes adopt their final orientation over a few hours,^{6,7} so all liposome samples were left to equilibrate for at least 1 day before data collection.

2.2 | Sample orientation and data plotting

DNA and liposome samples were flow oriented in a microvolume Couette flow cell with a sample pathlength of 0.5 mm.^{8,9} The SR light beam is focussed onto the center of the capillary in the cell, using a lens to produce a light spot of approximately 1 mm wide and 2 mm high. LD and FD-LD flow data are plotted as the difference between rotating (3000 rpm) and non-rotating spectra of the same sample. For the preparation of sample films, plastic ziplock bags were used to provide uniform polyethylene films which were stretched by a factor of ~ 3.75 in a custom-made film stretcher.¹⁰ Films were transferred to the holder illustrated in Figure 1. All data are plotted as if the molecular orientation axis were \parallel . This means transitions aligned with the stretch direction of the films, or the DNA helix axis, or the membrane normal (the lipid orientation) are expected to have positive LD. As LD

FIGURE 1 A custom-made 3D printed film holder for films pre-stretched in the film stretcher of reference¹⁰.

measures the photons which *are not* absorbed and FD-LD measures the emission of those that *are* absorbed, in the absence of any complexities due to quantum yield, the FD-LD is expected to mirror the LD.

2.3 | Spectrometer

The measurements were carried out on the AU-CD beam line of the ASTRID2 synchrotron light source at the Department of Physics and Astronomy, Aarhus University, Denmark. Light taken from a dipole magnet source is monochromatised using a 400 l/mm toroidal grating, with an exit slit defining the desired photon energy, with a resolution better than 0.5 nm. In a nitrogen purged end station, mounted after a high quality CaF₂ window, the monochromatised light passes through a MgF₂ Rochon polarizer (B. Halle) to ensure that only horizontally polarized light is passed through the photoelastic modulator (PEM, Hinds Instruments). The sample chambers are custom-made and purpose built to contain either the Couette flow cell or stretched film holder for LD (and FD-LD) measurement or a temperature-controlled sample chamber for CD measurement. Filters for FD-LD and FD-CD measurement were placed after the sample, before the PMT detector in a 3D-printed holder. Although in practice the stretch direction of the film holder was vertical, we present the data as if the stretch direction aligns with the horizontal \parallel polarization of light. High-quality long-pass filters were chosen to cut-off

light beyond the absorbance region of any sample. There is usually about 10 nm below the nominal cut-off where the FD-LD is distorted, so where the fluorescence intensity is high enough it can be advantageous to use a longer wavelength cut-off filter and start the FD-LD data collection at longer wavelength than the beginning of the fluorescence band. LD signals were measured via a lock-in amplifier operating the PMT under constant DC bias/varying HT and converted to ΔOD . The conversion was based on a Jasco calibration unit utilizing the differential reflection from two tilted quartz plates. The FD-LD and fluorescence signals were recorded at constant PMT HT, and the data presented here are the direct lock-in (FD-LD) and DC level (fluorescence) signals from the detector amplifier (V). Details of HT and the long-pass filters used for each dataset presented are given in the figure captions. Flow-oriented lipid samples present a strong wavelength dependent scattering in the LD signal. Rayleigh scattering correction was applied to these samples as in reference Dawes et al.,¹¹ and in all cases, both the as measured and the corrected spectra are shown. We note that FD-LD signals do not need corrections due to the long wavelength of the fluorescence photons.

3 | RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data and discussions below indicate what can be accomplished with a synchrotron light source which maintains its intensity down to about 170 nm and has

FIGURE 2 Overlay of linear dichroism (LD), fluorescence-detected linear dichroism (FD-LD), absorbance, and fluorescence (DC) for naphthalene (0.13 mg/ml in chloroform) dropped on one side of a stretched polyethylene film. For FD-LD measurements, a fixed high voltage (HV) of -850 V was applied to the photomultiplier tube (PMT) detector and a 325 nm filter (Semrock BLP01-325R-25) placed between the sample and PMT. Data are plotted so that stretch direction aligns with \parallel polarization.

high quality optics. The main advantage for samples oriented in stretched films and for flow-oriented DNA samples is that we can measure down to nearly 170 nm (depending on the film or Couette cell cut-offs). The flow-oriented phosphatidyl choline liposomes made with low purity lipids only gain about 10 nm with respect to a bench-top instrument due to the impurities in the lipid. However, the collimated nature of the SR light beam means that (nearly) all the fluorescent photons in the forward direction hit the detector even with the lensing effect of the LD capillary and light scattering of the liposomes so the non-rotating samples have little or no apparent FD-LD in contrast to our previous work.³

As noted above, the data have been plotted so the unique axis (film stretch direction or membrane normal or DNA helix) is the parallel direction. Parallel-polarized transitions thus have a positive LD and negative FD-LD.

3.1 | Naphthalene

Naphthalene is a simple fluorophore composed of two fused benzene rings that give it a sufficiently high aspect ratio to orient well on films. There are limited naphthalene LD data in the literature such as in earlier studies^{12, 13} and no FD-LD. Figure 2 shows representative LD, FD-LD, absorbance and fluorescence spectra of naphthalene on a stretched polyethylene film. The LD and FD-LD are almost mirror image—even to the vibronic structure. The magnitude of the 220 nm FD-LD relative to the 270 nm region is about one third of the LD due to the lower quantum yield of the band. The FD-LD is more reliable at the low wavelength end of the spectrum due to absorbing impurities in the film and the challenge of baseline subtraction. Conversely, LD is better at the longer wavelength where there is no interference from the filter. Finally, it should be noted that both the FD-LD and LD signs need careful consideration as the short (270 nm) and long (220 nm) axis polarized transitions both have the sign expected for long axis transitions (positive LD and negative FD-LD) indicating the vibronic coupling to the long-axis band thus dominates the short-axis polarized transition (see below for anthracene). Davidsson and Nordén soaked naphthalene into films and for polyethylene saw a small negative LD at 290 nm which was absent with polypropylene.¹³ This indicates that the “solvent” (in this case the film and any neighboring naphthalene molecules) affects the degree of coupling.

3.2 | Pyrene

Pyrene is a widely used fluorophore¹⁴ with more complex optical behavior than that of naphthalene, though it

retains the same D_{2h} symmetry so its in-plane transitions are either long-axis or short-axis polarized. Literature polarizations are as follows: 340 nm long, 275 nm short, and 240 nm long.^{10,14,15}

The mirror image FD-LD and fluorescence spectra of pyrene flow-oriented in liposomes (Figure 3A) are better resolved than our previous data³ and over a wider wavelength range. The long wavelength extension

FIGURE 3 Overlay of linear dichroism (LD), fluorescence-detected linear dichroism (FD-LD), absorbance, and fluorescence (DC) for pyrene. For FD-LD measurements, a fixed high voltage (HV) of -700 V was applied to the photomultiplier tube (PMT) detector and a 364 nm filter (Semrock BLP01-364R-25) placed between the sample and PMT. Data are plotted so the membrane normal (the molecular orientation direction) is the //polarization. (A) Flow-oriented lipids (0.12 mg/ml pyrene, 9 mg/ml PC, 1:20 M ratio). (B) Stretched polyethylene (0.4 mg/ml in chloroform dropped on one side film and then washed until the signal was on scale). (C) A pyrene-pyrene oligomer consistent with the observed film spectra.

TABLE 1 Anthracene band signs with // plotted to make the anthracene long axis transitions LD positive and FD-LD negative.

ASTRID2 FD-LD nm	Film FD-LD sign	Film LD sign	Lipid FD-LD	Lipid LD	Literature assignments
379	+	–	+	–	$^1B_{1u}$
374(sh)	+	–	Sh apparent in fl. but zero in FD-LD	–	
361	+	–	+	–	
357	+	Not clear if max or min	Sh apparent in fl. but zero in FD-LD	+	
365	– (or minimum)				
352	–	–			
346(sh)	–	+			
341	–	+	+	–	
321(sh)	–		+		
310	–	+	+		
298	–	Sh+			
256	–	+	–		$^1B_{2u}$
250	–	+	–		?Rydberg or weak valence
219	+	–	+		$^1B_{1u}$
207	–	Sh+			$^1B_{2u}$ ²¹
190(sh)	+	+			$^1B_{2u}$
187	+	+			$^1B_{1u}$

Abbreviations: FD-LD, fluorescence detected linear dichroism; LD, linear dichroism.

is due to the fact that we were able to collect data with a higher wavelength cut-off filter due to the more intense light beam. The higher beam intensity also enabled us to collect data to 210 nm rather than 220 nm showing a positive FD-LD and negative (relative to the scattering background) LD (short axis) 210 nm band. The band signs are consistent with literature assignments^{10,14,15} with the exception of the small positive FD-LD and negative LD (short axis) bands at 343 which are to the long wavelength side of a large peak so may indicate the presence of aggregates coupling to yield lower energy bands opposite in sign from the main band.¹⁰ The 248–290 nm region is complex as initially noted by Thulstrup et al. in 1970 who proposed 360 nm showed vibronic coupling with the 240 nm (long axis polarized) band.¹⁶ Although predominantly negative/positive LD/FD-LD, there are clear positive/negative components.

The pyrene film data (Figure 3B) are beautiful from 350 nm to nearly 170 nm with largely mirror image FD-LD and LD spectra (except at low wavelength where LD baseline correction is challenging due to impurities in the film). However, in contrast to the liposome spectra, the signals for the short-axis polarized bands (below 210 nm, 250–280 nm) are small and of the “wrong” sign.¹⁷ Based on the work of Thulstrup

et al.,¹⁶ we expected a large negative LD and positive FD-LD at 275 nm. They prepared their samples by soaking chloroform into the polyethylene, whereas we simply dropped on the surface of the polyethylene which allows it to assemble into higher order structures.¹⁸ Assuming any energy splitting between and exciton bands is small (so we combine in-phase and out-of-phase) and the orientation is uniaxial, then from Razmkhah et al.¹⁰ (supporting information), for twist angle 2γ

$$LD^r(\text{long axis}) = S(1 + \cos^2(2\gamma)) \quad (4)$$

$$LD^r(\text{short axis}) = S(1 - 3\cos^2(2\gamma)) \quad (5)$$

So, if the ratio of LD^r's is about ~ 5 (or more), then $2\gamma \sim 60^\circ$ (or more). Figure 3C is consistent with this speculation.

3.3 | Anthracene

We previously measured LD and FD-LD of anthracene on films and in liposomes.^{1,3,10} Gudipati et al.¹⁹ with

FIGURE 4 Overlay of linear dichroism (LD), fluorescence detected linear dichroism (FD-LD), absorbance, and fluorescence (DC) for anthracene. For FD-LD measurements, a fixed high voltage (HV) of -850 V was applied to the photomultiplier tube (PMT) detector and a 405 nm filter (Semrock BLP01-405R-25) placed between the sample and PMT. Data are plotted so the membrane normal (the molecular orientation direction) is the // polarization. (a) Flow-oriented lipids (0.025 mg/l anthracene, 1.7 mg/ml PC, 1:16 M ratio). (b) Stretched polyethylene (0.4 mg/ml in chloroform dropped on one side film and then washed until the signal was on scale). (c) Time evolution of the FD-LD spectrum for a film of anthracene, with the sample slowly evaporating away from the film.

reference to prior research^{20,21} provide a good summary of anthracene spectroscopy some of which forms the basis for the literature assignments of Table 1. In their own work, they used the polarized light of a synchrotron source and matrix isolation for the sample (15 K argon).

The FD-LD of the lipidic samples (Figure 4A) are noisy but have clear features down to ~ 210 nm, whereas previously,³ the spectrum was only clear to about 240 nm. We are working at one sixth of the concentration of our earlier work. In contrast to our previous work, the non-rotating baselines on the SR-based setup have small FD-LD signals making baseline correction relatively straightforward. As plotted, the 370 nm transition FD-LD vibronic components are all positive and the LD negative in accord with this transition being short-axis polarized and perpendicular to the membrane normal. Thus, the lipids dampen the vibronic coupling with the intense long-axis 256 nm band that we see on films (Figure 4B).

By using a synchrotron light source, we were able to extend our previous film FD-LD measurements by 55 nm and increase their resolution. The different vibronic couplings affect the quantum yields differently, and the patterns of the 300–370 nm region are slightly different in the FD-LD and LD, with the FD-LD having a bit less short-axis intensity. At the low wavelengths, the intensity of the B_{2u} transition dominates the LD, whereas the B_{1u} dominates the FD-LD. Figure 4C shows data as a function of time or equivalently loading of analyte on the film due to the volatility of polyaromatic hydrocarbons.

FIGURE 5 (A) Overlay of linear dichroism (LD), fluorescence detected linear dichroism (FD-LD), absorbance, and fluorescence (DC) for DAPI (30 μ M) with DNA (500 μ M), and LD and absorbance of DNA alone. (B) Overlay of LD, FD-LD, absorbance, and fluorescence (DC) for PI (63 μ M) flow oriented by binding to DNA (500 μ M). (C) Overlay of CD, FD-CD, absorbance, and fluorescence for DAPI (9 μ M) and DNA (180 μ M) measured in a 10 mm path length cuvette. For FD-LD (FD-CD) measurements, a fixed high voltage (HV) of -850 V (-800 V) was applied to the photomultiplier tube (PMT) detector and a 405 nm filter (Semrock BLP01-405R-25) placed between the sample and PMT. Data are plotted so the flow direction (DNA helix axis) aligns with // polarization.

3.4 | DNA flow orientation of 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole and propidium iodide (PI)

Figure 5A shows the FD-LD, LD, fluorescence, and absorbance of DNA-DAPI (4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole) from about 400 to 170 nm, 30 nm lower than in Wemyss et al.². The DAPI shows a broad negative FD-LD band from 300 nm until the filter cut-off mirroring the positive LD. A series of overlapping bands which are hidden under the DNA signals in the LD are apparent in the FD-LD. Based on where fluorescence (previously unobtainable) and FD-LD maxima are, there are seven peaks: negative at 200, 232, and 268 nm and positive at 187, 214, 250, and 279 nm. There are some literature data available in this region,^{1,2,22} but based on this, they (including our own previous work) have all missed some peaks. It should be noted that comparing film and DNA bound LD (and FD-LD) signs is difficult for a low symmetry molecule such as DAPI unless transitions are clearly assigned and the DNA binding geometry known.

Despite being deemed a replacement for ethidium bromide as a fluorescent DNA stain, PI's fluorescence below 300 nm was a disappointment being very low in magnitude; though the spectra (Figure 5B) behaved as expected for an intercalator being positive for all transitions, we observe under the DNA bands. The value of complementary techniques is illustrated in Figure 5C where DAPI-DNA FD-CD is plotted. It shows fluorescence maxima at 194, 229, 267, perhaps 292 nm and FD-CD positive maxima at 190, 243, and 285 nm and negative maxima at 202, 217, 266 nm thus clearly

confirming the existence of all the bands suggested above from the FD-LD except 234 and 252 nm which are probably also present given the mismatch in wavelengths of fluorescence and positive FD-LD maxima.

4 | CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have shown that the AU-CD beam line on the ASTRID2 synchrotron, which has been adapted for LD, can successfully measure FD-LD spectra of higher quality than a bench-top instrument on a range of samples. In general, the wavelength range is extended though only by 10 nm for our chosen lipid sample which has absorbing impurities. DNA-ligand FD-LD spectra approached 170 nm which is a bit better than the 180 nm of our previous synchrotron LD work⁸ as did the film samples. The fairly uniform light intensity over the wavelength range as well as the small uniform beam which hit the center of the samples rather than the >8 mm beam of our previous work meant I_o had no impact on the relative FD-LD magnitudes of different transitions, making low wavelength bands appear significantly more intense than in our previous work.¹⁻³ Mean low wavelength fluorescence and FD-LD signals are larger. We also saw the absence of scattering artifacts mainly due to the fact that the fluorescence occurs at longer wavelength than the absorbance and scattering has an inverse wavelength dependence,²³ so the emitted light is scattered (significantly) less than the unabsorbed light measured in the LD experiment. Somewhat to our surprise, we found that the SR light source gave better resolved spectra than previously. We attribute this to the smaller light beam and thus averaging over fewer sample ensembles. The ASTRID2 data also benefit from the advantage of FD-LD over LD in that the baseline is not an issue, and it probes only oriented (bound) fluorophores thus giving selectivity. Finally, one of the major advantages of the SR-experiment is that it collected high-quality fluorescence spectra at the same time as the LD which was not possible on our bench-top instrument, so in the latter case, we were unable to make use of wavelength shifts between fluorescence and FD-LD.

The focus of this work has been to show the merits of SR FD-LD spectra. However, it should also be apparent that FD-LD needs to be complemented by other spectroscopic techniques and depending on the questions being asked a wide range of other techniques. We found LD and CD data essential even to understand the relatively familiar molecules of this work and for DAPI-DNA FD-CD provided valuable complementary information. Circularly polarized luminescence and linearly polarized luminescence also provide complementary data for chiral

and oriented fluorophores^{24,25} as do infra-red and Raman spectroscopies.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Nykola C. Jones: Conceptualization; data curation; formal analysis; visualization; writing - original draft; methodology; investigation; supervision; project administration; writing - review and editing; software; validation; funding acquisition; resources. **Alison Rodger:** Conceptualization; data curation; formal analysis; visualization; writing - original draft; writing - review and editing; project administration; supervision; investigation; methodology; software; validation; funding acquisition; resources. **Søren V. Hoffmann:** Conceptualization; data curation; formal analysis; visualization; writing - original draft; writing - review and editing; project administration; supervision; investigation; methodology; software; validation; funding acquisition; resources.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data available on repository ([10.5281/zenodo.10709521](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10709521)).

ORCID

Nykola C. Jones <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4081-6405>
 Alison Rodger <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7111-3024>
 Søren V. Hoffmann <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8018-5433>

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